

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-179-AD-H-2% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	88	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 179
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/13/2022 20:45:10 CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 20:35:42 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.432	301770	28.26	11886
2	12.583	295545	27.68	10923
3	13.882	235062	22.01	7765
4	15.808	235386	22.04	7149

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-223-ADH-2% asy (0.1%)	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20230310
Vial:	6	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 223
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/10/2023 10:18:18 CST		
Date Processed:	3/10/2023 10:48:42 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.526	3011751	95.63	118158
2	12.746	5895	0.19	392
3	13.992	71332	2.26	2562
4	16.152	60555	1.92	1999